

A Reaching Law for Non-linear Sliding Surface: New Variable Power Exponential Rate Reaching Law (VPERRL)

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Abstract

To increase the efficacy and stability of the non-linear Reaching-Sliding Mode Controller (RSMC), this study presents a new reaching law for non-linear sliding surfaces. Previous research has focused on improving the reaching time to fully leverage the robustness property of sliding mode motion. The system dynamics in many real applications, however, are non-linear, and conventional RSMC may not provide satisfactory results. This restriction is addressed by the new reaching law for non-linear sliding surfaces, which adopts a more adaptable strategy. Attention has also been on alleviating and/or eliminating Unwanted Chattering Phenomena (UCP) during sliding mode motion so that smooth control is obtained which will not hinder practical applications. To achieve the desired, this new reaching law has redefined the reaching phase. So that by dividing the reaching phase into variable phases, the control law gains the ability to bring the system state closer to the non-linear sliding surface sooner. This greatly reduces the impact of uncertainties and Bounded Unknown External disturbances (BUE-disturbances). Another thing is that it gives the control law the ability to change the method of convergence of the system state in such a way that it reaches the non-linear sliding surface with a decreasing speed. Exponential Rate Reaching Law (ERRL) and Power Exponential Rate Reaching Law (PERRL) are two methods reported in the literature for alleviating chattering in sliding mode. The contribution of this study introduces a new Variable Power Exponential Rate Reaching Law (VPERRL) that offers significant improvements in reaching time and chattering reduction compared to ERRL and PERRL. Thus, the proposed new reaching law offers multiple benefits, including improved chattering reduction, decreased reaching time, and ensuring the system state settles at its final position with a considerable improvement in speed of response.

Keywords: Reaching-Sliding Mode Controller (RSMC), Reaching Law, Sliding Mode Controller (SMC), Constant Rate Reaching Law (CRRL), Variable Power Exponential Rate Reaching Law (VPERRL).

1. Introduction

1.1. Background and motivations

The motivation for proposing a new reaching law is to reduce the impact of uncertainties and BUE-disturbances during the reaching phase. In the Constant Rate Reaching Law (CRRL), the system state is affected by uncertainties and BUE-disturbances from the time it starts moving until it reaches the non-linear sliding surface. Therefore, the designer should make the system state go through this phase faster to reach the non-linear sliding surface. However, the problem is that if it hits a non-linear sliding surface at this high-speed, it will pass and create Unwanted Chattering Phenomena (UCP). As a result, it prompted the authors to divide the reaching phase into two phases [1] : In the first reaching phase, the system state should go through at a high-speed. In the second reaching phase, the system state will reach the non-linear sliding surface with a lower speed so that will enter with greater convergence to the sliding phase. This was the motivation behind the proposal new reaching law.

1.2. Literature review for reaching law

RSMC is a type of Variable Structure Control (VSC) that has received significant attention from control engineers. RSMC is based on the design of discontinuous control laws that switch to drive the system trajectories to the non-linear sliding surface [2]. The literature offers numerous non-linear control techniques such as feedback linearization [3], backstepping [4] [5], adaptive-backstepping [6] [7] [8], fuzzy feedback linearization [9], and RSMC [10] which falls under the VSC family.

Table 1 presents some of the nonlinear rules that researchers have reported in recent years.

Table 1 - Types of non-linear Rate Reaching Law

Reference No.	Abbreviation	Type of non-linear reaching law
[1] [11] [12] [13]	(CRRL)	Constant Rate Reaching Law
[14] [15]	(ERRL)	Exponential Rate Reaching Law
[16] [17] [18]	(PERRL)	Power Exponential Rate Reaching Law
[19] [20]	(VPERRL)	Variable Power Exponential Rate Reaching Law

At RSMC, the system state takes time to reach the non-linear sliding surface, allowing uncertainties and BUE-disturbances to affect its condition. To address this issue, researchers introduced the PERRL method [16] [21]. PERRL modifies the "Power Reaching Rate term" in ERRL to create an integrated attainment rule that combines the properties of both PRRL and ERRL. The PERRL method increases the speed at which the system state reaches the non-linear sliding surface in order to minimize the negative effects of uncertainties and BUE-disturbances. However, this increased speed can also result in the system state hitting the non-linear sliding surface at a higher speed than the RSMC method, potentially leading to increased Unwanted Chattering Phenomena (UCP). This behaviour occurs because PERRL does not provide a smooth transition between control measures when the system state is close to the non-linear sliding surface. To address this issue, the VPERRL method proposes dividing the reaching phase of the system state to the non-linear sliding surface into two phases.

1.3. Contributions

Building on existing research, this study introduces a new VPERRL method aimed at enhancing the reaching phase and control input. The main contributions of this paper are as follows:

1. A new reaching law called VPERRL is introduced to expedite the system's approach to the non-linear sliding surface. This law consists of two parts: The first part involves the system state reaching high speeds to transition to the second part of the reaching law. In the second part, which is in close proximity to the non-linear sliding surface, the system state aims to converge to this surface. The benefits of each part are extensively discussed in the paper.
2. The new reaching law proposed is simulated for a second-order dynamical system. A comparison is also conducted between the performance of the proposed law and several other reaching laws using the same dynamic system to demonstrate its superior performance.

1.4. Paper organization

Section 1 introduces the study, covering the background, motivations, literature review on reaching laws, and the contributions of the research. Section 2 discusses the Reaching-Sliding Mode Controller (RSMC) approach, including its disadvantages, structure, sliding function design, Unwanted Chattering Phenomena (UCP), and reaching law design for sliding surfaces. Section 3

presents the basic mathematical and structural system model, focusing on the conventional RSMC approach. Section 4 details the design of reaching laws with variable parameters, including naming conventions, velocity analysis in the reaching phase, and introduces the New Variable Power Exponential Rate Reaching Law (VPERRL) along with convergence time and steady-state buffeting analyses. Finally, Section 5 concludes the study by summarizing key findings and implications.

2. RSMC approach

The RSMC design process involves selecting a non-linear sliding surface with the necessary motion characteristics, choosing discontinuous control, enforcing the state to reach this surface, and establishing a sliding mode. The sliding mode is governed by an equation with Lipschitz's continuous right-hand side, which allows for the application of any design method from conventional control theory. The second issue deals with non-trivial reduced-order stability resulting from discontinuities in control, The RSMC design process involves selecting a non-linear sliding surface with the necessary motion characteristics, choosing discontinuous control, enforcing the state to reach this surface, and establishing a sliding mode. Sliding mode is governed by an equation with Lipschitz's continuous right-hand side, allowing for the application of any design method from conventional control theory. The second issue deals with non-trivial reduced-order stability resulting from discontinuities in control, as well as reaching and existence conditions. This indicates that the design methodology for RSMC is mainly developed in the context of "reaching conditions". The main objectives of this development are to estimate the reaching time and achieve finite-time convergence to the non-linear sliding surface [22]. From this perspective, RSMC can be considered as a systematic and effective robust control approach for maintaining system stability and performance in the presence of modelling uncertainties and BUE-disturbances. RSMC is a typical technique for VSC and is essentially a kind of special non-linear control, and its non-linear performance is characterize by the discontinuity in control. Due to its strong robustness, RSMC is widely utilized in uncertain systems.

2.1. Disadvantages of RSMC approach

Here are some disadvantages of RSMC:

Unwanted Chattering phenomena (UCP) : Chattering is a prevalent issue in RSMC that can result in increased wear and tear on mechanical systems, as well as noise and vibration in electrical systems [23].

Modelling errors and BUE-disturbances: The high switching frequencies and significant control effort required by RSMC can be a disadvantage in the presence of BUE-disturbances and large modelling errors.

Uncertain convergence time: The convergence time of RSMC can be uncertain, making it difficult to predict the behaviour of the control system [24].

Control effort: RSMC does not set restrictions on control effort, which may lead to increased control activity and potentially cause issues related to system wear and energy consumption.

Singularity: The discontinuous character of the control law in RSMC is the cause of the singularity. This can result in the control input becoming unbounded or infinite when the system operates near the non-linear sliding surface. Consequently, RSMC can suffer from singularity, leading to instability and poor performance [24].

2.2. Structure of RSMC approach

In practice, symbolic simplification is utilized to replace complex n-order problems with simpler 1st-order problems. This approach is referred to as first-order RSMC. First-order RSMC comprises of two separate control laws: Equivalent continuous control during the reaching phase and switching discontinuous control during the sliding phase (see Figure 1 and Figure 2).

Figure 1 – Reaching phase and Sliding phase

Figure 2 – Control block diagram of Reaching-Sliding Mode Controller

2.3. Sliding function Design

To minimize tracking errors and output deviations in order to achieve a satisfactory surface, it is essential to utilize an appropriate non-linear sliding surface when designing RSMC for practical applications [2]. Consider a second-order non-linear system as follows [3]:

$$\dot{x} = f(x) + g(x)u \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{f}(\cdot)$ is an unknown non-linear function and $0 < \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x})$. The $\mathbf{x} = [x_1 \ x_2] \in \mathcal{R}^n$ is the system state variables and $u(\mathbf{x}, t) \in \mathcal{R}^m$ is the control input as a function of state and time. Let the desired output be denoted as \mathbf{x}_d and the tracking error as \mathbf{e}

$$\mathbf{e} = \mathbf{x}_d - \mathbf{x} \quad (2)$$

Design the differential equation of an asymptotically stable or sliding function $s(\mathbf{x}) = 0$ with $n = 2$.

$$s(\mathbf{x}) = \left(\frac{d}{dt} + \lambda\right)^{n-1} \mathbf{e} = \left(\frac{d}{dt} + \lambda\right)^{2-1} \mathbf{e} = \dot{\mathbf{e}} + \lambda \mathbf{e} = (\dot{\mathbf{x}}_d - \dot{\mathbf{x}}) + \lambda(\mathbf{x}_d - \mathbf{x}) = 0 \quad (3)$$

where $0 < \lambda$ is a non-linear sliding surface parameter and a strictly positive constant, and this gain parameter determine the slope of the non-linear sliding surface $s(\mathbf{x}) = 0$. For differential equation as

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}_1 = x_2 \\ \dot{x}_2 = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) + \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x})u \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

then

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{s}(\mathbf{x}) &= \ddot{\mathbf{e}} + \lambda \dot{\mathbf{e}} = \ddot{\mathbf{x}}_d - \ddot{\mathbf{x}}_1 + \lambda \dot{\mathbf{e}} = \ddot{\mathbf{x}}_d - (\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) - \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x})u) + \lambda(\dot{\mathbf{x}}_d - \dot{\mathbf{x}}_1) \\ \dot{s}(\mathbf{x}) &= (\ddot{\mathbf{x}}_d + \lambda(\dot{\mathbf{x}}_d - \dot{\mathbf{x}}_1) - \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})) + \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x})u \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

If $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})$ and $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x})$ are known. The control law is designed as

$$u_{eq} = \frac{1}{\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x})} (\ddot{\mathbf{x}}_d + \lambda(\dot{\mathbf{x}}_d - \dot{\mathbf{x}}_1) - \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})) \quad (6)$$

$$u_{sw} = \frac{1}{\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x})} (K \cdot \text{sign}(s)) \quad (7)$$

$$u = u_{eq} + u_{sw} = \frac{1}{\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x})} (\ddot{\mathbf{x}}_d + \lambda(\dot{\mathbf{x}}_d - \dot{\mathbf{x}}_1) - \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})) + \frac{1}{\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x})} (K \cdot \text{sign}(s)) \quad (8)$$

From (5) and (8) :

$$\dot{s} = -K \cdot \text{sign}(s) \quad (9)$$

where $0 < K$ is a positive constant, it should be sufficiently large to suppress all uncertainties and unpredictable system dynamics [25]. The reaching condition can be achieved by selecting $\dot{s} = -K \cdot \text{sign}(s)$, which is known as the *Constant Rate Reaching Law (CRRL)*. It is important to note that this also ensures invariance, if assuming $\text{sign}(0) = 0$.

Design a Lyapunov pseudo-energy function $V(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{2}s(\mathbf{x})^2$. From (3) and (9):

$$\dot{V}(\mathbf{x}) = s\dot{s} = -s \cdot K \cdot \text{sign}(s) = -K \cdot |s| \leq 0, \quad \text{for } s(\mathbf{x}) \neq 0. \quad (10)$$

Then, $\dot{V}(\mathbf{x}) \leq 0$. The closed system is asymptotically stable, $s(\mathbf{x}) \rightarrow 0$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$, then $e \rightarrow 0$ and $\dot{e} \rightarrow 0$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$. The convergence precision is dependent on K . If $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})$ is unknown, it is possible to estimate $\mathbf{f}(\cdot)$ by using algorithms.

If $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})$ is unknown, it is possible to estimate $\mathbf{f}(\cdot)$ by using algorithms.

Despite the advantages of RSMC, chattering is a harmful phenomenon caused by unmodeled dynamics or discrete-time implementation. It can lead to undesirable results, including low control accuracy, high heat losses in power circuits, and excessive wear of moving mechanical parts. Although chattering is a main characteristic of RSMC, it is effective in dealing with uncertainties and BUE-disturbances.

2.4. Unwanted Chattering phenomena (UCP)

Chattering is particularly unwanted for systems and actuators as it can lead to actuator failure and unnecessarily large control signals. Due to the presence of time delays, such as time delays, time lags, dead time, transportation lag, and physical constraints, conventional RSMC algorithms do not allow actuators to switch at an infinite frequency along a non-linear sliding surface $s(\mathbf{x}) = 0$. Several approaches have been proposed to address chattering, aiming to eliminate control discontinuity and achieve exponential stability. *Shokouhi-Markazi function* [26], Saturation functions, sigmoid functions, hyperbolic tangent functions, and hysteresis saturation functions are commonly chosen alternatives to relay control [2]. Therefore, adding a boundary layer to the sign

function $sign(\cdot)$ can smooth abrupt changes and reduce Unwanted Chattering phenomena (UCP). This approach is referred to as a *soft Reaching-sliding mode controller*. In this study, to prevent excessive chattering in control input, the *Shokouhi-Markazi function* is used as an approximation instead of the sign function. This approximation has also been utilized by other researchers [27] [28] [29] [30] [31] [32].

$$sign(s) \cong \frac{s}{\sqrt{s^2 + \gamma}}, \quad 0 < \gamma \quad (11)$$

2.5. Reaching law design for sliding surface function

The term "reaching law" was originally used in relation to non-linear systems by Gao et al. [33]. The approaching motion's dynamic performance can be enhanced by the reaching law. It is a differential equation that specifies the dynamics of a sliding surface function $\dot{s}(\mathbf{x})$. Additionally, the dynamic quality of the system in the reaching phase can be controlled by choosing the parameters in the differential equation. The reaching law also establishes a reaching condition and directly describes the dynamics of the sliding surface function $\dot{s}(\mathbf{x})$.

For the RSMC approach, several types of reaching laws have been proposed in the literature (see Table 1). However, designing a controller to reduce Unwanted Chattering Phenomena (UCP) is crucial which motivates research for a new reaching law presented in section 4.3.

3. Basic Mathematical and Structural System Model

An important class of the linear systems are time-invariant systems. Mathematically, they can be described by a linear function which does not depend on time, i.e. a first-order vector differential equation:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{f}[\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t)]; \quad \forall 0 \leq t; \quad \mathbf{u}(t) \neq 0 \quad (12)$$

where $\mathbf{x}(t)$ is n -dimensional column state vector of the system states, $\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathcal{R}^n$; $\mathbf{u}(t)$ is m -dimensional column input vector of the system excitations, $\mathbf{u}(t) \in \mathcal{R}^m$. \mathbf{f} is linear vector function of independent variables $\mathbf{x}(t)$, $\mathbf{u}(t)$, and t is a scalar variable (time), $t \in \mathcal{R}_+$.

To utilize RSMC and assess the efficacy of the reaching laws, let's examine the dynamic equation provided belows

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}_1 = x_2 \\ \dot{x}_2 = u \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

3.1. Conventional RSMC approach

Based on the feedback linearized dynamic system, the conventional RSMC approach is applied to compute the control input u . This is done by considering a regulation problem, where the closed-loop error is defined as follows:

$$e = x_d - x_1 \xrightarrow{x_d=0} e = -x_1 \quad (14)$$

Hence, the sliding function can be proposed as (15) where λ is a positive parameter with a value of 2.

$$s(\mathbf{x}) \doteq \left(\frac{d}{dt} + \lambda \right)^2 e = \dot{e} + \lambda e = \dot{e} + 2e \quad (15)$$

From (14) and (15) :

$$s \doteq \dot{e} + 2e = -\dot{x}_1 - 2x_1 = -x_2 - 2x_1 \quad (16)$$

4. Design of the reaching law with Variable-parameters

4.1. Naming of Reaching Laws

Since the reaching law is designed separately from the non-linear sliding surface $s(\mathbf{x}) = 0$, RSMC can directly benefit from its use. In short, every reaching laws should meet the following three crucial requirements:

1. The reaching law's strategy should guarantee system robustness.
2. A high-convergence rate of the system state should be guaranteed when it is far from the equilibrium point.
3. The system state should guarantee finite-time convergence when it is close to the equilibrium point.

Remark: It should be noted that any law that better satisfies these three crucial requirements will be more widely accepted.

For continuous-time systems, reaching laws are named based on certain elements. The fundamental elements of a reaching law usually include s , $|s|$, $sign(s)$, an exponential term $|s|^\alpha$, and an integral term. The combination of these components, as well as the combination of two or more reaching laws, determines the name of the final reaching law.

In general, each element in Table 2 illustrates how the reaching law is named:

Table 2 – The basis for naming the reaching laws in RSMC [34]

Elements	Naming symbol
s	Fast/Quick/Proportional Rate term
$sign(s)$	Constant Rate term
$s + sign(s)$	Fast Constant Rate term
$ s ^\alpha$	Exponential Rate term
$ s .sign(s)$	Power Rate term
$ s ^\alpha.sign(s)$	Power Exponential Rate term
$ s ^{\alpha_1}.sign(s) + s ^{\alpha_n}.sign(s)$	Double-Power Exponential Rate term
$ s ^{\alpha_1}.sign(s) + \dots + s ^{\alpha_n}.sign(s)$	Multi-Power Exponential Rate term
$s + s ^\alpha.sign(s)$	Fast Power Exponential Rate term
$s + s ^\alpha.sign(s) + s ^\alpha.sign(s)$	Fast Double-Power Exponential Rate term
$s + s ^{\alpha_1}.sign(s) + \dots + s ^{\alpha_n}.sign(s)$	Fast Multi-Power Exponential Rate term
$\begin{cases} s ^\alpha.sign(s) \\ s s ^\alpha \end{cases}$	Variable-Power Exponential Rate term

4.2. Velocity analysis in the reaching phase

The reaching process of the system can be divided into two phases: the phase away from the non-linear sliding surface $s(\mathbf{x}) = 0$, and the phase close to the non-linear sliding surface. Figure 3 schematically shows the stages of reaching the non-linear sliding surface $s(\mathbf{x}) = 0$ taking into account the variability of the reaching law. The figure illustrates the four stages of the reaching law's variability in approaching this surface.

Figure 3 – Four stages of movement of system state by changing the motion regime.

According to Figure 3:

Stage 1: The $\Delta < s$ is based on the reaching law $s \rightarrow +\Delta$. As a result, according to (19), the system state quickly moves towards stage 2. In $s = +\Delta$, the results of reaching laws (19) and (20) are equal.

Stage 2: During $0 < s \leq \Delta$, the movement regime of the system state changes from stage 1 to stage 2. The system current state is represented by (20). In step 2, the $s = \Delta$ is based on the reaching law $s \rightarrow 0^+$.

Stage 4: The $s < -\Delta$ is based on the reaching law $s \rightarrow \Delta^-$. As a result, according to (18), the system state quickly moves towards stage 3.

Stage 3: During $s = -\Delta$, the movement regime of the system state changes from stage 4 to stage 3. The system current state is represented by (17). In step 2, the $s = -\Delta$ is based on the reaching law $s \rightarrow 0^-$.

4.3. New Variable Power Exponential Rate Reaching Law (VPERRL)

The primary objective of this study is to design a controller that can effectively handle uncertainties and BUE-disturbances. This objective was achieved by utilizing the RSMC approach, which is one of the VSC approaches. Furthermore, a new approximation (11) was

employed to minimize or eliminate Unwanted Chattering Phenomena (UCP) around the non-linear sliding surface $s(\mathbf{x}) = 0$. Based on the VSC method, a new "reaching law of variable structure" was introduced in this study. This law belongs to the new "VPERRL" category, as depicted in Table 2.

The area surrounding the non-linear sliding surface $s(\mathbf{x}) = 0$ is referred to as the quasi-sliding domain band, denoted by $0 < \Delta$. In Figure 3, the boundary between stages 1 and 2 is indicated by $+\Delta$, while the boundary between stages 3 and 4 is indicated by $-\Delta$. The two stages of the reaching phase are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &+\Delta \leq \text{reaching phase 1} \\
 &0^+ \leq \text{reaching phase 2} \leq +\Delta \\
 &\text{Reaching phase 4} \geq -\Delta \\
 &-\Delta \leq \text{reaching phase 3} \leq 0^-.
 \end{aligned}$$

Based on the data provided, the proposed "New Variable Power Exponential Rate Reaching Law" is as follows:

$$\dot{s} = \begin{cases} -K \cdot (\text{sign}(s) + \psi s), & 0 < K, \psi, \text{ if } \Delta \leq |s| \\ -K \cdot \text{sign}(s)(1 + \psi |s|^\alpha), & 0 < \alpha < 1, 0 < K, \psi, \text{ if } |s| < \Delta \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

$$(18)$$

For reaching laws (17) and (18), the system states s and \dot{s} can converge to the equilibrium zero in a finite time, that is, $s = \dot{s} = 0$ after a finite time.

By inserting (11) in (17) and (18):

$$\dot{s} = \begin{cases} -Ks \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{s^2 + \gamma}} + \psi \right), & 0 < K, \psi, \text{ if } \Delta \leq |s| \\ -\frac{Ks(1 + \psi |s|^\alpha)}{\sqrt{s^2 + \gamma}}, & 0 < \alpha < 1, 0 < K, \psi, \text{ if } |s| < \Delta \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

$$(20)$$

By increasing the value of $0 < \psi$, the speed of convergence to the non-linear sliding surface $s(\mathbf{x}) = 0$ in new VPERRL in the Reaching phase 2 (stage 2) increases. Initial condition is $x_1 =$

3.5, $x_2 = 5$, and other parameters values as follows: $K = 8, \alpha = 0.2, \gamma = 0.02$, and $\lambda = 3$ (Figure 4).

Figure 4 – The new VPERRL with changes in the value of $0 < \psi$

The advantages and disadvantages of the new VPERRL compared to CRRL are as follows. It is crucial to keep in mind that these advantages and disadvantages are general observations and could change based on specific implementation details and system characteristics:

A- Advantages of new VPERRL:

1- Fast convergence: If the system state is far from the non-linear sliding surface $s(\mathbf{x}) = 0$, in the new VPERRL, the system state reaches this surface sooner. In other words, in Figure 3, step 1 is completed earlier. The power exponential nature of the reaching law ensures rapid convergence towards the origin. This can be advantageous in time-critical systems where a quick response is essential.

2- Flexibility: The new VPERR allows the convergence rate to be adjusted according to specific requirements of the system. This flexibility enables improved control and optimization in various applications.

3- Smooth control: The variable power feature allows for smooth and continuous control, avoiding sudden changes or oscillations in the system response. This can result in improved stability and reduced overshoot.

4- Reducing/eliminating chattering: Unwanted Chattering Phenomena (UCP) occurs in step 2 of Figure 3. In the new VPERRL, both due to the use of the new approximation (11) and the power exponential nature of the reaching law, these phenomena have a lesser impact.

B- Disadvantages of new VPERRL:

1- Complexity: Implementing a new VPERRL may require more complex mathematical calculations and programming compared to simpler control laws. This complexity can increase the development time and effort.

2- Tuning challenges: Determining appropriate values for the power parameter can be challenging, as it requires a good understanding of system dynamics and performance requirements. Improper tuning may result in suboptimal control or instability.

3- Sensitivity to parameter variations: The performance of a new VPERRL can be sensitive to variations in system parameters or BUE-disturbances. Small changes in these factors may affect the convergence speed or accuracy.

4- Limited applicability: While suitable for many applications, there may be certain systems where a new VPERRL is not well-suited due to specific requirements or constraints. In such cases, alternative control laws may be more appropriate.

4.3.1. Convergence Time Analysis for new VPERRL

The basic principle of RSMC is the existence of a sliding mode. The motion of the system should tend to switch at the non-linear sliding surface $s(\mathbf{x}) = 0$, which implies that conditions for existence and accessibility satisfy $s\dot{s} < 0$ [19] [35].

Theorem 1. The accessibility condition is satisfied for the system described in reference [1].

For reaching laws (22) and (23), the system state can reach the equilibrium point $s(0,0) = 0$ under its action. In the continuous system, if the sliding mode approach law exists and $s\dot{s} \leq 0$ is satisfied

with the reachability conditions [36] [37], then the designed sliding mode approach law exists. This means that the system states can reach equilibrium under the action of both laws (22) and (23).

Proof. A Lyapunov function is considered:

$$V(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{2}s(\mathbf{x})^2 \quad (21)$$

According to the conditions mentioned in (21)

$$\dot{V}(\mathbf{x}) = s\dot{s} = \begin{cases} -Ks^2\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{s^2 + \gamma}} + \psi\right), & 0 < K, \psi, \text{ if } \Delta \leq |s| \\ -\frac{Ks^2(1 + \psi|s|^\alpha)}{\sqrt{s^2 + \gamma}}, & 0 < \alpha < 1, 0 < K, \psi, \text{ if } |s| < \Delta \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

$$(23)$$

When and only when $s(0,0) = 0$, there is $s\dot{s} = 0$.

According to the Lyapunov stability theory, (22) and (23) show that the system under consideration is stable and that the sliding mode's convergence is guaranteed. Additionally, it is possible to guarantee the motion quality of the system state in the process of approaching the sliding mode by adjusting the power coefficient under various conditions.

Theorem 2. For reaching law (17) and law (18), the system states s and \dot{s} can converge to the equilibrium zero in a finite time, that is, $s = \dot{s} = 0$ after a finite time.

Proof. Suppose the initial condition $+\Delta = 1 < s(0) = s_0$.

1) For stage 1:

In (17), based on the fact that the value is $sign(s) = 1$ and the reaching law can be expressed as (Figure 3)

$$\dot{s} = -K \cdot (1 + \psi s), \quad 0 < K, \psi \quad (24)$$

$$\int_0^{t_1} dt = \int_{s_0}^1 \frac{1}{-K(1 + \psi s)} ds \quad (25)$$

Therefore, the time t_1 used for $s(0) = s_0 \rightarrow s = 1$ can be obtained as

$$t_1 = -\frac{\ln|1 + \psi| - \ln|1 + s_0\psi|}{K\psi}, \quad 0 < K, \psi \quad (26)$$

Suppose $\psi = 1$ as

$$t_1 = -\frac{\ln|2| - \ln|1 + s_0|}{K}, \quad 0 < K \quad (27)$$

2) For stage 2:

In (18), based on the fact that the value is $sign(s) = 1$ and $s = 1 \rightarrow s(t_2) = 0$, and the reaching law can be expressed as (Figure 3)

$$\dot{s} = -K(1 + \psi s^\alpha), \quad 0 < \alpha < 1, \quad 0 < K, \psi \quad (28)$$

$$\int_0^{t_2} dt = \int_1^0 \frac{1}{-K(1 + \psi s^\alpha)} ds \quad (29)$$

$$t_2 = \frac{1}{K} \int_0^1 \frac{1}{(1 + \psi s^\alpha)} ds \quad (30)$$

Suppose $\psi = 1$ as

$$t_2 = \frac{1}{K} \int_0^1 \frac{1}{(1 + s^\alpha)} ds \quad (31)$$

The value of the integral (30) or (31) strongly depends on the value of α . Suppose $\Delta = 1$ and $\psi = 1$ and knowing the integral (31) for the $\alpha = 0.1$ value as

$$\begin{aligned} t_2 &= \frac{1}{K} \int_a^b \frac{1}{(1 + s^{0.1})} ds \quad (32) \\ &= \frac{1}{K} \left(9 \left(\frac{1}{8} b^{\frac{8}{9}} - \frac{1}{7} b^{\frac{7}{9}} + \frac{1}{6} b^{\frac{2}{3}} - \frac{1}{5} b^{\frac{5}{9}} + \frac{1}{4} b^{\frac{4}{9}} - \frac{1}{3} b^{\frac{1}{3}} + \frac{1}{2} b^{\frac{2}{9}} - b^{\frac{1}{9}} + \ln |b^{\frac{1}{9}} + 1| \right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - 9 \left(\frac{1}{8} a^{\frac{8}{9}} - \frac{1}{7} a^{\frac{7}{9}} + \frac{1}{6} a^{\frac{2}{3}} - \frac{1}{5} a^{\frac{5}{9}} + \frac{1}{4} a^{\frac{4}{9}} - \frac{1}{3} a^{\frac{1}{3}} + \frac{1}{2} a^{\frac{2}{9}} - a^{\frac{1}{9}} + \ln |a^{\frac{1}{9}} + 1| \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

Formula (31) based on different values of α is as follows (Table 3):

Table 3 – Different values of t_2 for $0 < \alpha < 1$ changes

α	t_2
$\frac{1}{9} = 0.1$	0.53K
$\frac{1}{5} = 0.2$	0.55K
$\frac{1}{3} = 0.33$	0.58K
$\frac{1}{2} = 0.5$	0.62K
...	...

In summary, combining (27) and (31), the total time for the system to move from any initial state $s = s_0$ to the non-linear sliding surface $s(\mathbf{x}) = 0$ is T , which can be calculated by

$$T = t_1 + t_2 = -\frac{\ln|2| - \ln|1 + s_0|}{K} + \frac{1}{K} \int_0^1 \frac{1}{(1 + s^\alpha)} ds. \quad (33)$$

When the initial state of the system is $+ \Delta = 1 < s(0) = s_0$, the proof is the same as the above one; that is, the system can reach equilibrium state from any initial position in finite time. Furthermore, according to reaching law (17) and law (18), when $s = 0$, it can be got that $\dot{s} = 0$.

4.3.2. Steady-state buffeting analysis

For reaching law (19) and law (20), because all the components of the formula contain s , when $s = 0^+$ and $s = 0^-$, reaching law (19) and law (20) can be obtained by integration $\dot{s}(0^+) = \dot{s}(0^-) = 0$ as $\dot{s} = 0$, i.e. the system will not produce buffeting when it is near the steady-state.

4.3.3. Simulation Results and Discussion

The most important application of phase portraits in RSMC is to analyze the stability and behavior of the system. Phase portraits play a crucial role in understanding and optimizing RSMC systems by providing insights into stability, convergence, oscillatory behavior, and Unwanted Chattering Phenomena (UCP).

Phase portrait of four reaching laws with $\Delta = 1$ and initial condition are $x_1 = 3.5$, $x_2 = 5$ and other parameters values as follows: $K = 3$, $\alpha = 0.2$, $\gamma = 0.02$, $\psi = 1$, and $\lambda = 3$ and BUE-disturbances are not considered. (Figure 5).

$$CRRL: \dot{s} = -K \cdot \text{sign}(s) = -\frac{Ks}{\sqrt{s^2 + \gamma}} \quad (34)$$

$$PRRL: \dot{s} = -K \cdot |s| \cdot \text{sign}(s) = -\frac{K \cdot s \cdot |s|}{\sqrt{s^2 + \gamma}} \quad (35)$$

$$PERRL: \dot{s} = -K \cdot |s|^\alpha \text{sign}(s) = -\frac{K \cdot s \cdot |s|^\alpha}{\sqrt{s^2 + \gamma}} \quad (36)$$

$$VPERRL: \dot{s} = \begin{cases} -Ks \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{s^2 + \gamma}} + \psi \right), & 0 < K, \psi, \text{ if } \Delta \leq |s| \\ -\frac{Ks(1 + \psi|s|^\alpha)}{\sqrt{s^2 + \gamma}}, & 0 < \alpha < 1, 0 < K, \psi, \text{ if } |s| < \Delta \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

$$(20)$$

Figure 5 – Phase portrait of four reaching laws with $\Delta = 1$

5. Conclusions

Different types of reaching laws are categorized. The author of this study presented these categories in the form of tables (Table 1 and Table 2). Based on these categories, a new VPERRL was proposed that outperformed previous reaching laws in the same category. The proposed reaching law divides the reaching phase into two phases. Each phase is further divided based on the proximity of the system state to the non-linear sliding surface $s(\mathbf{x}) = 0$. These reaching laws also include parameters that allow the designer to control how the system states reach the non-linear sliding surface $s(\mathbf{x}) = 0$ by adjusting these parameters.

Nomenclature

Abbreviation	Term
(BUE-disturbances)	Bounded Unknown External disturbances
(CRRL)	Constant Rate Reaching Law
(ERRL)	Exponential Rate Reaching Law
(FCRRL)	Fast Constant Rate Reaching Law
(PERRL)	Power Exponential Rate Reaching Law
(RSMC)	Reaching-Sliding Mode Controller
(SMC)	Sliding Mode Controller
(UCP)	Unwanted Chattering Phenomena
(VPERRL)	Variable Power Exponential Rate Reaching Law
(VSC)	Variable Structure Control

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